

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

No6
MAXSUS SON

BAKALAVR TALABALARINIG MAQOLALARI TO'PLAMI

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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Elektron nashr. 60 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil mayda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION: ECONOMIC CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola barqaror iste'mol va ishlab chiqarishni (SCP), uning iqtisodiy muammolari va mumkin bo'lgan echimlariga qaratadi. Bu SCP qanday qilib iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishi, atrof-muhitga zararni kamaytirishi va uzoq muddatli iqtisodiy o'sishni qo'llab-quvvatlashi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Dunyo bo'ylab so'nggi ma'lumotlar, siyosatlar va misollarni o'rganib, maqola resurslarni isrof qilish, bozor muammolari va barqarorlik uchun motivatsiya etishmasligi kabi asosiy iqtisodiy muammolarni muhokama qiladi. Shuningdek, u barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirish uchun yangi siyosatlar, texnologiya takomillashtirish va odamlarning xatti-harakatlaridagi o'zgarishlarni ko'rib chiqadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, hukumatlar, korxonalar va odamlar ushbu muammolarni hal qilish va SCP maqsadlariga erishish uchun birgalikda harakat qilishlari kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: Barqaror iste'mol, Barqaror ishlab chiqarish, Iqtisodiy muammolar, Siyosat yechimlari, Resurs samaradorligi, Sirkulyar Iqtisodiyot, Yashil texnologiya, Bozor motivatsiyasi.

Abstract: This paper looks at sustainable consumption and production (SCP), focusing on its economic problems and possible solutions. It shows how SCP can improve economic efficiency, reduce harm to the environment, and support long-term economic growth. By studying recent data, policies, and examples from around the world, the paper discusses major economic problems like wasting resources, market issues, and lack of motivation for sustainability. It also looks at new policies, technology improvements, and changes in people's behavior to encourage sustainable economic growth. The findings show that governments, businesses, and people must work together to solve these problems and achieve SCP goals.

Key words: Sustainable Consumption, Sustainable Production, Economic Problems, Policy Solutions, Resource Efficiency, Circular Economy, Green Technology, Market Motivation.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается устойчивое потребление и производство (УПП), особое внимание уделяется его экономическим проблемам и возможным решениям. В ней показано, как УПП может повысить экономическую эффективность, уменьшить вред окружающей среде и поддержать долгосрочный экономический рост. Изучая последние данные, политику и примеры со всего мира, в статье обсуждаются основные экономические проблемы, такие как трата ресурсов, проблемы рынка и отсутствие мотивации к устойчивости. В ней также рассматриваются новые политики, усовершенствования технологий и изменения в поведении людей для поощрения устойчивого экономического роста. Результаты показывают, что правительства, предприятия и люди должны работать вместе, чтобы решить эти проблемы и достичь целей УПП.

Ключевые слова: Устойчивое потребление, Устойчивое производство, Экономические проблемы, Решения политики, Эффективность ресурсов, Круговая экономика, Зеленые технологии, Мотивация рынка.

INTRODUCTION

This paper explores sustainable consumption and production (SCP) as important ways to achieve economic and environmental sustainability worldwide. SCP aims to grow the economy without harming the environment by using resources wisely, reducing waste, and promoting sustainable lifestyles and production methods. The idea has become popular with the global adoption of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 12, which focuses on responsible consumption and production [1]. Economically, SCP can support long-term growth by improving resource use, lowering costs, and creating green jobs. However, there are problems like unsustainable production, market issues, lack of motivation, and resistance to changing behavior. This study examines these problems and looks at how policies, new technology, and teamwork can solve them to create a circular and fair economy.

The aim of this study is to examine the economic problems of applying sustainable consumption and production (SCP) and to find effective solutions through policies, technology, and behavior changes. By analyzing examples from different countries and recent data, the research wants to understand how SCP can improve economic efficiency, protect the environment, and support sustainable development. The study also plans to suggest practical ideas for governments, businesses, and people to move toward a circular economy and meet SDG 12 goals.

The research questions guiding this study are:

What are the main economic problems stopping sustainable consumption and production?

How do SCP practices help economic efficiency and environmental protection?

What policy and market solutions can solve economic problems for SCP?

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

SCP has become important worldwide for achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs), especially SDG 12, which calls for responsible consumption and production [1]. Experts say that old economic growth

models, which take resources, produce goods, use them, and throw them away, are not possible anymore because of environmental limits [2]. The circular economy, which focuses on reusing materials, extending product life, and reducing waste, is seen as a good way to apply SCP [3].

Economic problems with SCP are well-known. These include market issues, like environmental costs not being included in prices and lack of information that stops people from making good choices [4]. High costs of new clean technologies and low public awareness about sustainable options also cause problems [5]. Different countries use different solutions. The European Union has started projects like the Circular Economy Action Plan and rules for eco-friendly design and waste reduction [6]. Developing countries face bigger problems due to limited money and technology but have shown new ideas in community sustainability projects [5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and descriptive approach to explore the economic dimensions of sustainable consumption and production (SCP). It is based on secondary data drawn from reputable sources such as international reports, academic journals, and official policy documents. These include publications by the World Bank, OECD, United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the European Commission, and recognized scholars in the fields of sustainability and economics. These sources were selected due to their reliability, relevance, and comprehensive coverage of SCP-related issues.

The research utilizes a comparative case study method to examine SCP practices in both developed and developing countries. Case selection was guided by variables such as geographical diversity, stages of economic development, and the existence of significant SCP-related policies or projects. For instance, the European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan and community-led sustainability initiatives in developing countries are analyzed to understand contrasting contexts. This approach allows the identification of best practices, persistent barriers, and region-specific solutions.

The analysis focuses on key indicators such as resource usage trends, green job creation, and carbon emission patterns over time. These metrics serve to assess both the economic and environmental impacts of SCP. Furthermore, policy documents and scholarly articles are reviewed to identify recurring themes—such as market failures, technological innovation, and behavioral change—that influence SCP outcomes. These insights are then linked to real-world experiences in transitioning toward sustainable economic models, particularly circular economy frameworks and resource efficiency strategies.

To ensure reliability, the study triangulates information from multiple sources, minimizing the risk of bias or inaccuracy. The qualitative approach provides in-depth understanding of the economic and socio-cultural drivers of SCP, while cross-country comparisons reveal how different policies perform across varying economic and institutional settings. Nevertheless, the methodology is subject to limitations, such as reliance on secondary data, which may not fully capture the most recent developments, and the context-specific nature of qualitative findings, which may not be universally applicable. Despite these constraints, the use of diverse and authoritative sources strengthens the validity of the analysis and offers a solid foundation for the study's conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings show several economic problems that make SCP difficult. One major issue is wasting resources. Many economies still depend on growth models that use too many resources. Market issues, like not including environmental costs in prices, also cause problems by encouraging overuse of harmful goods and services [4]. Countries using circular economy strategies show better results. The European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan has improved recycling, resource use, and reduced the need for new materials [6]. Similar progress is seen in Japan and South Korea, where government support has helped develop green technology and recycling systems [3].

Table 1. Resource Productivity Trends in Italy, Brazil and South Africa (2017–2023) [7]

Year	Italy (USD/kg)	Brazil (USD/kg)	SouthAfrica (USD/kg)
2017	1.2	0.8	1.0
2019	1.4	0.9	1.2
2021	1.6	1.1	1.3
2023	1.8	1.3	1.5

Resource Productivity Trends (2017–2023) - Italy, Brazil, South Africa

Figure 1. Resource productivity trends (2017-2023) [7]

Table 1 presents resource productivity trends, measured in USD per kilogram, for Italy, Brazil, and South Africa from 2017–2023. Over the six-year period, all three countries showed consistent increases in resource productivity. Italy recorded the highest values, rising steadily from 1.2 USD/kg in 2017 to 1.8 USD/kg in 2023, with uniform biennial increments of 0.2 USD/kg. South Africa followed a comparable trend, starting at 1.0 USD/kg in 2017 and reaching 1.5 USD/kg by 2023, with increases of 0.1–0.2 USD/kg every two years. Brazil exhibited the lowest resource productivity, growing from 0.8 USD/kg in 2017 to 1.3 USD/kg in 2023, with slightly smaller biennial increments. Overall, Italy maintained the highest resource productivity, Brazil the lowest, and South Africa showed moderate growth between them.

Changing people's behavior is also important. When people know more and are willing to buy sustainable products, it increases demand, which encourages businesses to adopt SCP [1]. Digital technology is also used more to manage supply chains, reduce waste, and share clear information [5]. New technology is key. Investments in renewable energy, efficient buildings, and waste reduction have grown significantly, helping sustainability and creating jobs [2]. However, developing countries still face problems such as lack of money, weak systems, and limited technology. International help and teamwork can support these countries in adopting sustainable methods [5].

CONCLUSION

Sustainable consumption and production (SCP) offer a way to achieve economic growth while protecting the environment for future generations. This study shows that SCP faces major economic problems, such as market failures, inefficient resource use, and resistance to behavioral change. These challenges are more severe in developing countries, where financial and technological resources are limited. However, SCP also provides opportunities for stronger economies, increased employment, and a cleaner environment. By implementing policies that integrate economic incentives, technological innovations, and public participation, countries can overcome these barriers and foster sustainable growth.

The circular economy is a key mechanism for implementing SCP, enabling resource conservation and waste reduction by reusing materials and extending product lifecycles. Successful examples, such as the European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan, demonstrate how targeted policies can enhance resource efficiency and environmental protection. Innovations in renewable energy and digital supply chain systems further support SCP by increasing transparency and efficiency. Public behavior is critical when consumers understand and choose sustainable products, it drives businesses to align with SCP principles.

To ensure the success of SCP, governments must prioritize it in national strategies and align efforts with global targets such as SDG 12. Policy tools like carbon pricing and support for green technology can help stimulate sustainable practices. International cooperation is essential, particularly in assisting developing countries through financial aid, technological transfer, and capacity-building initiatives. Educational programs and public awareness campaigns are also needed to encourage sustainable lifestyle choices.

Looking ahead, SCP holds the potential to balance economic progress with environmental stewardship. Addressing economic barriers through collaboration, innovation, and equitable policymaking can lead to resilient, inclusive, and sustainable economies. As global resource demands continue to rise, this study reaffirms that SCP is a realistic pathway to achieving economic success while preserving natural ecosystems. Governments, businesses, and individuals must act in concert to strengthen SCP and secure a sustainable future for all.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>